

Deliverable D1.7

Project communication strategy - final evaluation and review

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1. Executive Summary

This document presents the final evaluation of the GDI project communications, as defined in *D1.2 GDI Project communication strategy*¹ and *D1.5 Project communication strategy – update and evaluation*². It presents quantitative data to measure the effectiveness of GDI communications and dissemination activities between November 2024 and December 2025.

The evaluation draws on data from the project website, newsletters and social media platforms (X and LinkedIn). Dissemination indicators, including participation in external events, publications and project outputs on Zenodo, are also evaluated. These data provide an overview of how the GDI project has communicated its project objectives and outputs to key stakeholders and wider audiences. The results of the evaluation show that the project has effectively implemented the D1.2 and D1.5, sharing project highlights across main communications channels.

The website continued to serve as the primary communication channel for the project information, highlighting the project's technical progress, collaboration with other EU projects and sustainability plan. The newsletter remained an effective way to communicate project results, with an increase in subscriber numbers. There is a significant improvement in social media engagement, especially LinkedIn, since the last project communication strategy review in October 2024. As recommended in D1.5, the GDI project has increased posting frequency, curated thematic campaigns on project deliverables and promoted the project objectives and outputs through video content. These approaches led to substantial growth in LinkedIn followers, impressions and engagement rate. The paid LinkedIn campaign has also successfully extended the project's reach beyond the research community to policymakers, healthcare professionals and citizens.

Dissemination activities performed strongly with project partners actively presenting GDI results at conferences, workshops and meetings. Zenodo continued to function as the main repository for project outputs, achieving high levels of views and downloads and supporting open access and reuse.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/7862090>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/13930404>

The project successfully implemented four key improvements listed in D1.5: increasing and optimising social media activity, expanding newsletter outreach, monitoring engagement metrics and highlighting GDI outputs through engaging video content. The project will follow the strategy in D1.5 and continue to work on communications and dissemination activities to support sustainability and impact beyond the project.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'. For more details of project outcomes, see [here](#)]

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No

<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Methods

The project published a Project communication strategy (D1.2) in M6 of the project (April 2023) which outlined a strategy to communicate GDI project outputs, and an update and evaluation of the strategy (D1.5) in M24 of the project (October 2024). This document evaluates the updated communication strategy and reviews the outcomes of the project communications and dissemination activities from November 2024 to December 2025.

To provide the final evaluation of the communications strategy, we reviewed data from all communications channels, including:

- Website
 - Total unique pageviews and tracked pageviews
 - Unique pageviews per page
 - Number of news items
- Newsletter
 - Number of issues
 - Number of subscribers
 - Newsletter open rate and view rate
- Social media: X and LinkedIn
 - Number of posts
 - Number of followers
 - Engagement rate and impressions

We also evaluated the project's dissemination activities based on project partners' participation in external events as well as the publications on Zenodo.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Communications evaluation

4.1.1 Website

The GDI website remains the primary communication channel for the GDI project. It provides information about the vision and structure of GDI and updates on the project, including news releases, events and deliverables.

4.1.1.1 Website content

From November 2024 to December 2025, the project has six news articles on project highlights and one Stakeholder Forum event announcement. The topics of the news releases include technical demonstration videos, strategic collaboration with other EU projects and the long-term sustainability of the 1+Million Genomes Initiative.

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Table 1: List of news releases from November 2024 to December 2025

Release date	News release/event announcement title
17 December 2025	1+MG/GDI/B1MGplus Stakeholder forum: GDI outputs providing value to other EU dataspace projects today and in the future ³
13 October 2025	ERDERA and GDI work together to advance rare disease research and diagnostics ⁴
24 September 2025	Demonstrator video showcasing 1+MG federated analysis infrastructure - paving the way to federated learning ⁵
30 July 2025	Country representatives vote on interim and long-term sustainability ⁶
10 March 2025	Videos about the 1+Million Genomes Initiative released for citizens and healthcare professionals ⁷
3 March 2025	Strategic collaboration between GDI and Genome of Europe ⁸
17 February 2025	Two videos demonstrate GDI technical infrastructure ⁹

4.1.1.2 Website page views

The number of unique visitors to the GDI website in the period since the last GDI project communication strategy review was 12,601. The number of tracked pageviews was 21,670. The top three viewed pages of the GDI website are the project participants page, how the project is organised and outputs. It shows that the main focus of the GDI website visitors is information on the GDI project's organisation and its outputs, which remains the same from the results in D1.5.

Focusing on the news content page, the top three most viewed news items on the GDI website are the news on video demonstrations on GDI technical infrastructure, collaboration between GDI and Genome of Europe, and the vote on the project's long-term sustainability. It indicates that the audience is interested in the project's technical output and collaborations with other EU projects, as well as the sustainability and the development of the 1+MG infrastructure.

³ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/news/third-gdi-stakeholder-forum>

⁴ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/news/gdi-erdera-collaboration>

⁵ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/news/federated-analysis-infrastructure>

⁶ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/news/interim-and-long-term-sustainability>

⁷ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/news/1+mg-initiative-video>

⁸ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/news/collaboration-gdi-goe-mou>

⁹ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/news/gdi-technical-infrastructure>

Table 2: GDI website's top three visited pages

Page	Unique pageviews
/about/participants ¹⁰	260
/about/how-organised ¹¹	172
/outputs ¹²	165

Table 3: GDI website's top three viewed news

News title	Unique pageviews
Two videos demonstrate GDI technical infrastructure ¹³	354
Strategic collaboration between GDI and Genome of Europe ¹⁴	299
Country representatives vote on interim and long-term sustainability ¹⁵	244

4.1.2 Newsletter

The GDI newsletter for external stakeholders has been released quarterly since April 2023. From November 2024 to December 2025, there are 47 new subscribers, which brings the total subscriber number to 318. During this time period, the project released five regular newsletters and one special issue highlighting the outcome of the GDI Stakeholder Forum.

4.1.2.1 Newsletter engagement

The average open rate of the newsletter is 40.55%, and the average click rate is 12.16%, demonstrating a good level of engagement. Comparing the GDI newsletter engagement with the email marketing benchmark from Mailerlite¹⁶ shows that the average open rate of the GDI newsletter is slightly lower than the benchmark (43.46%), but the click rate is higher than the benchmark (2.09%). This suggests that the GDI newsletter subscribers who opened the newsletter are keen on clicking the link provided in the newsletter to read more information provided.

¹⁰ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/about/participants>

¹¹ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/about/how-organised>

¹² <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/outputs>

¹³ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/news/gdi-technical-infrastructure>

¹⁴ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/news/collaboration-gdi-goe-mou>

¹⁵ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/news/interim-and-long-term-sustainability>

¹⁶ <https://www.mailerlite.com/blog/compare-your-email-performance-metrics-industry-benchmarks>

When comparing with the last evaluation period (the first 24 months of the project), there is a slight decline in the newsletter open rate (58.15%) and click rate (20.40%). This could result from audience dilution as the subscriber base grows. The new subscribers often find the newsletter through events or social media. These subscribers might be more selective about their interested topics, hence not open or click on all newsletters they receive. An increase in subscribers with lower open and click rates could be interpreted as a successful dissemination, combined with natural audience diversification, not declining performance.

Table 4: GDI newsletter engagement comparison

	Nov 2024- Dec 2025	Nov 2022 - Oct 2024	Benchmark
Open rate	40.55%	58.15%	43.46%
Click rate	12.16%	20.40%	2.09%

4.1.2.2 Newsletter content

Analysing the top five clicked links in each newsletter issue, the most clicked contents are Stakeholder Forum information, project deliverables and project news. The GDI project videos on 1+MG Initiative and the technical demonstrators also accumulated a number of clicks and views in the newsletter.

4.1.2.3 Archive

All GDI newsletter issues are archived on the GDI website¹⁷.

4.1.3 Social media

The project's social media strategy focuses on community building and networking. An X account (@GDI_EUproject¹⁸) and LinkedIn account (Genomics Data Infrastructure¹⁹) were set up and managed by ELIXIR's Communications Officers from the start of the project. The main audiences targeted by social media are project partners, bioinformaticians, research scientists, infrastructure providers, data generators, policymakers and funders.

One of the key findings in D1.5 was the significant differences in follower numbers and engagement on GDI's X and LinkedIn accounts. With the drop in engagement and users in X and the larger followers on LinkedIn, the GDI project's social media strategy has a stronger focus on LinkedIn.

From September 2023, X (formerly Twitter) has stopped providing free analytics; therefore, this report will focus on LinkedIn analytics, such as followers, post engagement rate and impressions.

¹⁷ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/newsletter/>

¹⁸ https://x.com/GDI_EUproject

¹⁹ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/gdi-euproject>

4.1.3.1 Followers

By the end of December 2025, there were 2,570 followers on LinkedIn and 448 followers on X.

From November 2024 to December 2025, GDI has a steady growth in LinkedIn follower numbers, with over 1,000 new followers during this time period. This shows that social media campaigns throughout the year, including Deliverable of the Month, GDI technical demonstrator and 1+MG Initiative videos, have successfully attracted new audiences on LinkedIn.

Figure 1: GDI LinkedIn follower growth from November 2024 to December 2025

4.1.3.2 Post engagement

Between November 2024 and December 2025, 28 tweets were published on X and 38 original LinkedIn posts were published (not including shared posts).

The LinkedIn posts have attracted over 64,000 impressions and an average engagement rate of 0.067. The posts on X have attracted around 7,400 impressions, which shows that the GDI project reaches more audiences on LinkedIn. The table below is the list of five top performing LinkedIn posts:

Table 5: Sample of GDI top-performing LinkedIn posts from November 2024 to December 2025			
Date	Post/Link	Impressions	Engagement rate
30 July 2025	The legal framework for the sustainability of the 1+MG infrastructure has been defined, following a voting by representatives of countries participating	4,017	0.06

	in the GDI project. [...] ²⁰		
3 Mar 2025	👏 The European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) and Genome of Europe (GoE) have formally announced a strategic collaboration by signing a Memorandum of Understanding. [...] ²¹	3,923	0.057
13 Oct 2025	🚩 The European Rare Diseases Research Alliance (ERDERA) and the European Genomic Data Infrastructure project (GDI) are joining forces to speed up #raredisease research 🧬 and improve diagnosis across Europe. 👏 The collaboration will be launched on 14 October at a half-day workshop in Paris. [...] ²²	3,922	0.047
17 Feb 2025	👏 The European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project has released two videos 🎥 demonstrating how the 1+Million Genomes technical infrastructure can benefit scientists, patients and #healthcare providers. [...] ²³	3,498	0.067
9 Sept 2025	🚀 Today, the GDI project held its third General Assembly in Copenhagen, Denmark. 👏 The project partners gathered together onsite and online to present the achievements of the third year of the project implementation and discuss planning for the fourth year of the project. ²⁴	3,407	0.114

4.1.3.3 Special campaigns

As discussed in D1.5, the project has developed several social media campaigns around key project outputs to increase the frequency of posting and optimise social media platform engagement. From November 2024 to December 2025, the GDI project ran five special social media campaigns.

- **GDI October 2024 Deliverables social media campaign**
 - Duration: From November to December 2024
 - Number of posts: Six tweets and LinkedIn posts

²⁰ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7356254875212488704>

²¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7302268051524104192>

²² <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7383489219480174592>

²³ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7297195588406673411>

²⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7371173224635744256>

- Topic: The posts covered the key deliverables and milestones in October 2024, including technical developments of GDI, guidelines for national 1+MG communications and outreach strategy and support to the National Mirror Groups.
 - Result: On LinkedIn, the special campaign has an average of 1,299 impressions and 0.053 engagement rates.
- **GDI May 2025 Deliverables social media campaign**
 - Duration: May 2025
 - Number of posts: Two tweets and LinkedIn posts
 - Topic: The posts covered the two key deliverables from March to April 2025: the user portal live catalogue and recommendation of infrastructure solutions for distributed analysis and federated learning.
 - Results: On LinkedIn, the two posts have an average of 1,283 impressions and 0.06 engagement rates.
- **Demonstration of 1+MG technical infrastructure campaign**
 - Duration: February 2025 and September-October 2025
 - Number of posts: five tweets and LinkedIn posts
 - Results: The posts promoted the 1+MG technical infrastructure demonstration videos (for D3.6 and MS8) and the demonstration videos on the 1+MG analysis.
 - Results: On LinkedIn, the campaign has an average of 2,225 impressions and 0.053 engagement rates. The video on federated analysis for policymakers has over 750 views on LinkedIn.
- **1+MG video social media campaign**
 - Duration: March 2025 and October 2025
 - Number of posts: Six tweets and nine LinkedIn posts
 - Topic: The posts promoted the series of videos introducing the 1+MG Initiative, four interview videos with project stakeholders and the new GDI project "For citizens" page.
 - Results: On LinkedIn, the video campaign has an average of 1,752 impressions and 0.07 engagement rates. The series of four interview videos has an average of 894 views on LinkedIn.
- **1+MG videos paid-for LinkedIn campaign**
 - Duration: From 6 to 20 October
 - Number of posts: Four LinkedIn advertisement posts
 - Results: The two-week campaign consisted of four advertisement posts and was targeted at citizens, patient groups and healthcare professionals. The advertisement cost \$300 in total and has reached over 100K impressions on LinkedIn with over 130

clicks and an average of 0.21% click-through rate. During the two weeks of advertisement, the GDI LinkedIn page attracted over 100 new subscribers.

4.2 Dissemination evaluation

Dissemination is the process of ensuring all scientific outputs are openly available and in forms that are easily accessible, understandable and reusable. Dissemination fosters the use and uptake of results and outcomes. In contrast, communications covers the sharing and promotion of wider project efforts. Dissemination activities target audiences that are likely to use the results in their work, for instance, peers and experts in and outside of the project, including policymakers.

Communications activities target multiple audiences beyond the project consortium, including the media and the public. The dissemination activities described in D1.2 include external events and publications.

4.2.1 External events

By presenting at external events, the relevant scientific communities will be able to use the results and outcomes of the project in their work. From November 2024 to December 2025, the project partners have attended and presented at 21 conferences, meetings and workshops.

Table 6: Examples of five external events GDI project partners attended

Date	Event	Target groups	Objectives and outcomes
29 Jan 2025	Festival of Genomics & Biodata 2025	- Research communities - Industry	Presented how European infrastructure can support the discovery, access, sharing and analysis of human genomics data and linked phenotypic/other data on a massive scale.
18 Feb 2025	1+MG workshop on EHDS and legal sustainability	- Research communities - National authorities	The workshop explored the European Health Data Space Regulation and infrastructure, and options for the legal sustainability of 1+MG beyond the GDI project (long-term and short-term options).
23 May 2025	Genome of Europe and GDI, 1+MG alignment meeting	- Research communities - National authorities	Clarified responsibilities between GoE, GDI and 1+MG for harmonised data in discovery services.

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11 July 2025	GA4GH fireside chat	- Research communities	Serena Scollen (GDI project coordinator) joined the GA4GH fireside chat to talk about the current landscape of genomics and health and the GDI project's work.
15 Sep 2025	Netherlands Society for Human Genetics annual conference	- Research communities	Presented a poster on the importance of secondary use infrastructure, including Health-RI, 1+MG (GDI/GoE) and EHDS as interconnected infrastructure work related to human genetics.

4.2.2 Zenodo

Zenodo is used as a home for project outputs, such as deliverables, posters, presentation slides, training materials and other related documents. From November 2024 to December 2025, there were 31 documents uploaded to the GDI project's Zenodo community with a total number of 3,354 views and 3,039 downloads. Appropriate metadata, such as GDI project grant number and ORCID IDs of the authors, were added to all Zenodo uploads to ensure findability and project-wide aggregation by EC's OpenAIRE.

4.2.3 Publication

Publication helps increase awareness and publicity of technical knowledge resulting from project implementation. Between November 2024 and December 2025, a total of seven preprints and peer-reviewed publications were added to the GDI Dissemination activities tracker²⁵. The number of publications is not expected to be as high as other EU-funded research projects since the GDI project is focusing on implementation rather than research.

5. Discussion

Final review of the GDI project communications shows that the changes instigated following the interim review, particularly an increase in social media campaigns and an emphasis on original video content, have led to overall higher reach and engagement.

The most significant improvement of the project communications is in social media engagement. Since the last communications strategy review, the number of LinkedIn followers has grown by more than 1,000 and impressions increased substantially. LinkedIn engagement rates improved through

²⁵
https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1dtQwIS_LapIU5NQH7WHFADb2Nb2FHxG-DFZYH8GJwSI/edit?gid=882378210#gid=882378210.

the use of structured campaigns, visual content and short video formats. The special campaigns and the paid LinkedIn campaign demonstrate a proactive and targeted communications strategy that extends the project's audience from the research community to policymakers, healthcare professionals and citizens. Given the number of impressions and new followers, the paid LinkedIn campaign was judged to be a good use of project resources. For example, the average number of new followers per month is normally around 50 to 60, and the paid campaign gave over 100 in two weeks. The GDI LinkedIn page's monthly impressions range from 1000 to 10,000, depending on the frequency of posting whereas the paid LinkedIn campaign reached over 100,000 impressions.

Website analytics show sustained interest in pages describing project organisation, participants and outputs, confirming that visitors to the project website primarily seek structural information about GDI. The strong performance of news items related to technical demonstrations, collaborations with other EU initiatives and long-term sustainability highlights that the audience is particularly engaged with concrete outputs, interoperability and future impact of the project.

Newsletter performance illustrates a shift in audience. By sharing the subscription link and newsletter issue on social media and including the subscription QR code in the project's slides, the subscriber numbers have increased. The open and click rates declined as the subscriber base diversified, but click rates remained well above benchmarks, indicating the news items selected were relevant and of interest to subscribers. As the project progressed, the newsletter content emphasised more on project deliverables, milestones and video outputs. The project has successfully used the newsletter as a channel to communicate project results to stakeholders.

Dissemination activities show clear strengths. Participation in 21 external events ensured that GDI outputs were presented directly to relevant scientific, policy and infrastructure communities. Zenodo metrics demonstrate effective open-access dissemination, with high levels of views and downloads indicating strong reuse potential. Although publication numbers remain limited, this is consistent with the project's implementation-focused nature and does not indicate a shortfall in dissemination.

Looking towards the final phase of the project, the project will maintain engagement with audiences on social media with special campaigns on project outputs and technical demonstration videos. On the website, the project will continue to publish news releases highlighting project outputs and cross-linking to Zenodo resources to support discoverability and reuse. The project will continue to communicate project highlights and deliverables in the newsletter and, in this way, expand the outreach. The final issue of the project newsletter will further promote links to the GDI community on Zenodo, the GDI project website and the 1+MG Framework website for easy access of project outputs beyond the project lifetime.

6. Conclusions

The review of the project communication strategy focused on evaluating communications and dissemination activities between November 2024 and December 2025. The project has effectively

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implemented four key improvements mentioned in the D1.5 Project communication strategy - update and evaluation:

- Increase the frequency of social media posting and optimise the strategy
- Expand newsletter outreach
- Monitor engagement metrics
- Highlight GDI outputs through engaging video content

The evaluation shows that the GDI project has maintained high engagement and visibility on the project's main communications channels. GDI project's dissemination activities have successfully reached the key stakeholders and targeted audiences in the scientific and public sectors by participating in external events and conferences. The GDI community on Zenodo is the main platform to publish project deliverables and milestones and has accumulated over 3,000 views and downloads during this time period.

In the remaining months of the project, ELIXIR's Communications Officer will continue to work on the project's communications and dissemination activities to support sustainability and impact beyond the project. The main objectives for the communication in the remaining months are as follows:

- Maintain and strengthen social media engagement through targeted campaigns highlighting key project outputs and final results.
- Continue publishing news on the project website to showcase project outputs
- Strengthen cross-linking to Zenodo on the website to improve discoverability and reuse of project deliverables
- Sustain regular newsletter communications to highlight project milestones, deliverables and key messages for stakeholders
- Use the project newsletter to promote access to final outputs via Zenodo, the GDI website and the 1+MG Framework website, supporting impact beyond the project lifetime

